

Radio Frequency Magnetron Sputtered CuO:Al₂O₃ Thin Films for Gas Sensing Applications

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Abstract

In recent years, mixed metal oxide thin films have been greatly attracting the attention of the material science community because of their potential exploitation in various applications (1). Mixed CuO and Al₂O₃ thin films have been explored in several applications, yet their use in gas sensing field is unknown. We report the preparation of CuO:Al₂O₃ (50:50) thin film on quartz glass substrate by radio frequency magnetron sputtering technique with RF powers of 200 and 300 W at room temperature. X-ray diffraction study showed the deposited films were amorphous in nature. The average transmittance of CuO:Al₂O₃ (50:50) films in the visible region is around 80-90%. The RF power induced variation in energy band gap of 3.92 to 4.18 eV was observed. The CuO:Al₂O₃ (50:50) film showed good selective response to NH₃ gas with very high sensing response of 80.75 (10 ppm NH₃) at room temperature.

Keywords: Aluminium oxide, Copper oxide, Thin film, RF Sputtering, Gas sensor

Reference

1. N. Benito et al, Surf. Coatings Technol. 206(2011) 1484.